
Lord Macaulay's Recommendation on Education During British Rule in India: An Analysis

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ABSTRACT:

The paper examines the impact of Macaulay's Minute on Indians and on the Indian education. The impact may be seen in two forms, namely immediate impact and long term impact. This in turn helped in the material prosperity, social reform, rise of national consciousness, independence movement and finally in achieving Independence. The paper examines the inadequacies of the Indian Education Commission examined the education and suggested some improvements. Thoroughly it made suggestions for removing inadequacies. The paper explores the reason from maintaining English as the medium of education at the higher level is that it is a compulsion as well as the necessity.

KEYWORDS:

Education, Commission. Literature, Knowledge, System, British, Rule, Recommendation.

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Introduction:

British Education: The arrival of the British in India led to further changes in the social life and ideals. The British administration was keen only on strengthening its hold in the country. Consequently, Macaulay commented that the aim of their education was to create a class of individuals who were Indians only in colour and blood, but who were English in their interests, opinions, morality and intelligence. Schools. The British pattern of education turned out individuals good only for white collar jobs. Besides, they were also subjected to indoctrination in Christian principles. The above education system was changed by the Britishers according their own system of England and according to their need and philosophy. Advance system of education was incorporated. The monitoring of training and the semi formal system of teacher's training in India was noted by them. When the Britishers came, their major goal in the field of educate Indian children in British system. Formal system of teacher's education started by Britishers:

Lord Macaulay Recommendation on Education India: The British parliament had issued a new Charter to the East India Company in 1813. In this Charter the Company was directed to spend a sum of rupees one lacks on the maintenance and progress of literature, on the encouragement of the learned natives and on providing the knowledge of science to the Indians residing in the area under the Company's rule. "British education became firmly established in India with the founding of missionary schools during the 1820s" (Blackwell, 92) But the terms 'literature' and 'learned natives' were not defined clearly in this Charter. This issue gave birth to two schools of thought in the company first, Anglicists and second, Orientalists. Even in the British parliament two groups were formed over this issue. This controversy could not be solved even after 20 years in the new Charter Act of 1833. "Since the second half of the 20th century, Nationalists in India have criticised Macaulay his views on Hinduism and Indian culture at large, which they claim skewed his educational policies" (Christophe Jaffrelot 343)

On June 10, 1834 Lord Macaulay came to India as a law member of the Governor General's Council. He was a great scholar of English language and literature besides being a good orator and writer. "Many Indian nationalists have criticized Macaulayism, claiming that it uprooted Indian traditions in sectors such as finance and replaced them with a foreign system which was wholly unsuited to India. In addition, they claim that Macaulayism caused foreign systems of thought to become prioritized over Indian systems of thought, particularly Hindu systems of thought" (Thomas M. Leonard: 1119)

Long Term Impact of Macaulay:

Acquaintance of Western Literature, Knowledge and Science to Indians: The English medium and European knowledge and science oriented education system which was organised in India on the suggestion of Lord Macaulay led to the acquaintance of European literature, knowledge and science to the Indians and many benefits accrued to us.

Paved the Way for Material Prosperity in India: At the time of Macaulay, more emphasis was placed on social behaviour and spiritual development in Indian education but in the education system which was implemented on the suggestion of Macaulay attention was paid on the comprehensive progress of the country. This led to the material prosperity

of the country

Rise of Social Consciousness in India: During that period Indian society was infested with many social evils Macaulay laid the foundation of an education system which made Indians aware about these social evils. They made efforts to eliminate them and brought about many reforms in it.

Rise of Political Consciousness in India: The English System of Education made us aware about human rights, taught us the importance of freedom, equality and fraternity and developed political consciousness among us. Narullah and Nayak have aptly pointed out that but for the English education system Indian Independence movement would not have taken place.

Dominance of English Language in India: Besides the above mentioned merits Macaulay's Minute also had some negative consequences. The foremost among these was the increase in the domination of foreign language English. In fact the condition has now reached such an impasse that the more it is tried to weed out the more it becomes pervasive. It now seems that it is almost impossible to stamp out English from this country.

Entry of Western Civilization and Culture in India: There is nothing bad in accepting and assimilating the good aspects of any civilization and culture but to adopt other culture and detest one's own is to extinguish one's own identity. The education system proposed by Macaulay has left somewhat similar impact on us.

Macaulay many British scholars had also pointed out that East India Company should organize higher education only for the higher classes. Thereafter education will itself percolate down to the masses coming to contact with them. However, it was Macaulay who put forward this theory logically and emphatically which later on became the education policy of the Government. It was a very clever suggestion on his part. "Macaulay succeeded in replacing Persian with English as the administrative language through the English Education Act 1835, which established English as the medium of instruction and promoted the training of English-speaking Indians as teachers" (Blackwell, 92) "He was inspired by utilitarian ideas and advocated for what he referred to as "useful learning." (Catriona Ellis, 36)

In this way, we see that from the Indian point of view his report

contained more demerits than merits. From this point of view he and his report both are subjects of criticism

Immediate Impact of Macaulay's Minute:

- Declaration of Education Policy Macaulay's defined the section 43 of the Charter Act, 1813 and he defined it so cleverly and logically that Lord Bentinck, the then Governor General, agreed to it and declared the English medium and European knowledge and science oriented education policy. Thereafter all the subsequent education policies were formulated on its basis
- Beginning of the English System of Education: With the declaration of this education policy, English medium schools and colleges of higher education were opened. So strong was this foundation laid that this education system progressed rapidly in our country. Our present education system is also originally based on this education system.
- Declaration of English as the Official Language: In 1837, the then Governor General, Lord Auckland declared English to be the official language in place of Persian. It was the result of Lord Macaulay's logic given in the favour of English.
- English Compulsory for Government Jobs: In 1944, Lord Hardinge, the then Governor General, issued an order that at the time of appointment in government jobs candidates possessing the knowledge of English will be given preference. This preference became compulsory in practice

Macaulay's Intention:

Macaulay's argument was that the Oriental literature and knowledge is of very low standard, therefore to ameliorate the condition of Indians the education of English literature, knowledge and science is necessary and this education can be imparted through the medium of English language only "The term is derived from the name of British politician Thomas Babington Macaulay (1800-1859), who served on the Governor-General's Council and was instrumental in making English the medium of instruction for higher education in India" (Masani, Zareer 52)

But his real intention was to create a class of Indians who would be Indian by birth but English in taste and intellect. In his own words "We must at present do our best to form a class who may be interpreters

between us and the millions whom we govern, a class of persons Indian in blood and colour but English in opinion, in morals and in intellect." Not only this, his intention was to completely stamp out Indian religion, philosophy and culture. In his letter to his father he wrote "It is my firm belief that if our plans of education are followed up, there will not be a single idolator among the respectable classes in Bengal thirty years hence."

Evaluation of Lord Macaulay:

Evaluation of an object, idea or activity is done on some fixed or definite criteria. Macaulay report may be evaluated on three criteria—first, what was his real intention, second, to what extent his suggestions were beneficial to the Indians and third, to what extent its results benefitted Indians.

The recommendations of Lord Macaulay can be used follows:

- Oriental Literature and Learning is Useless Indian literature (Sanskrit and Arabic) and other Indian scriptures are full of superstitions and foolish talks. Its history mentions 30-foot-full rulers and oceans of juice and butter in geography. Its medical science is such that even English veterinarians would feel ashamed, and astrology can be laughed at by English school girls. Therefore, it is useless to undertake their teaching-learning. It is useless to spend government grants on Sanskrit and Arabic schools and colleges. It should be stopped henceforth
- Education of Occidental Literature and Learning is important: Macaulay opined that English literature was the best literature of the world. According to him, a single shelf of a good European library was worth the whole native literature of India and Arabia. Therefore, Indians should necessarily be taught English language and literature.
- Making English the Medium of Instruction is Essential: Macaulay has recommended to make English as the medium of instruction For this he gave the following reasons:
 - a. Undeveloped Native Vernaculars: The native vernaculars prevalent in India are unrefined and undeveloped, their vocabulary is limited and it is not possible to acquaint them with western learning and science through them.

- b. English Language: English comprises the best learning of the world Any person knowing English can know this vast mass of learning. Indians can be imparted this learning only through English.
- c. Sanskrit and Arabic: Sanskrit and Arabic are not the languages of masses nor are Indians interested to learn them. As compared to them, it is easier to learn English, so it should be made the medium of instruction
- d. English as the Medium of Instruction: English is the language of rulers as well as international trade. It is also the language of the high class Indians, so it should be made the medium of instruction
- e. Opinion of Enlightened Indians: Intelligent Indians, such as Raja Ram Mohan Roy etc., are of the opinion that English and western learning is essential for India's progress and development, so English should be made the medium of instruction.
- f. Education of Indian Law in English: Macaulay opposed making Arabic and Persian as the medium of instruction for teaching law, and said that Indian law should be translated into English and then taught thus
- Arrangement of Higher Education for Higher Classes: Macaulay has, in his minutes. Recommended government should provide for higher education only for higher classes He has given the following reasons for it:
 - a. It would create a class in India who will work as the messenger between the rulers (English) and the ruled (Indian m
 - b. Two classes will be made in India, the first being higher education class and the other deprived of higher education
 - c. The western culture adopted by the higher classes will impress those in the lower classes and they will adopt them in their lifestyle
 - d. The company will be able to get Indians to work on junior posta
 - e. Education will reach the lower classes through people of

higher classes in a natural way.

Policy of Essential in Religious Neutrality:

Education: Macaulay favoured introduction of western Christian religion, western European culture and learning among Indians, but he knew it well that direct and forceful effort in this direct could result in two fallouts:

- a. Indians would become active to preserve their religions and to further spread
- b. Indians would start opposing the English rule

So, he recommended not introducing any religion in education in schools.

Some scholars are of the opinion that the intention of Macaulay was really good, he indeed wanted the progress of Indians. Though it is another thing that the education system proposed by him also did some harm to us. Still the fact remains that the intention of Macaulay was not good, he wanted to replace the Indian literature, religion and philosophy with the western literature, religion and philosophy. Though it is another thing that the education system implemented in India, on the basis of the reform proposed by Macaulay benefited more than doing harm to us. The biggest benefit accrued of it was the beginning of the progressive education in place of the traditional education in our country.

Conclusion: The remarkable progress which we have achieved in the field of agriculture. Telecommunication and space technology are all the results of this English system of education. As far as the question of the increasing dominance of the foreign language, English and the increasing influence of the English civilization and culture is concerned, it too has benefited us in more than one way. It is because of the English language that the Indians, at present are pursuing higher education in India and in foreign countries, especially in the field of science and technology and are securing higher jobs abroad. The key to success in international trade is also this English language. Coming to the question of mass education we have adopted the regional languages as the medium of education after achieving independence. This has resulted in the expansion of mass education. This is the age of internationalism and instead of cursing Macaulay we must be thankful to him for all those benefits accrued of the English System of Education, western knowledge and science

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